

Road network simplification to support air quality analysis

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Summary

In this paper, we outline progress in ongoing work using the OpenStreetMap (OSM) street network dataset to support the analysis of hyperlocal (granular) air quality data in urban street networks. We use Dublin, Ireland, and Google Air Quality Lab data as our case study. To perform a road-based analysis of pollutant data collected by the Google Street View car, we address OSM network fragmentation by reconstructing roundabouts and aggregating road segments. Our approach creates a more cohesive representation of the streets under analysis while preserving key road attributes and resolving fragmentation issues.

KEYWORDS: Street Network Simplification, OpenStreetMap, Air Quality, Urban Analytics

1 Introduction and Motivation

Air quality is a critical public health and environmental concern (Reames and Bravo, 2019), especially in urban areas where transportation, industry, and human activity contribute to increased pollutants and particulate matter concentrations. These pollutants significantly impact human health (Manisalidis et al., 2020), contributing to cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, mortality, and overall reduced quality of life (WHO, 2023). In Dublin, Ireland, Google has partnered with Dublin City Council to collect hyperlocal air quality data using Google’s electric Street View car equipped with Aclima’s sensors. This dataset, available via Google Air Quality Lab¹, provides high-resolution measurements of six pollutants (NO, NO₂, O₃, CO, CO₂, PM_{2.5}) from May 2021 to August 2022, offering valuable insights for urban air quality analysis (Chen et al., 2024).

However, accurately assessing air quality along street networks requires a compact, coherent representation of each street. Previous studies have proposed various street network generalization approaches, often based on axial lines, street segments, or route structures (Marshall et al., 2018). For instance, Jiang and Claramunt (2004) study named-street centrality measures, simplifying the

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network by selecting streets based on graph properties. Differently, Porta et al. (2006) use an angle-based continuation approach to merge segments into longer roads, using solely geometrical data. Our approach builds on the concept of *cognitive space* (Penn, 2003) to achieve a representation of the street network that reflects human understanding of spatial configuration.

However, instead of axial lines, our methodology relies on street nomenclature and contiguity to reflect how humans cognitively categorize roads as contiguous entity. Unlike Jiang and Claramunt (2004), who focus on understanding graph properties through centrality measures without explicitly reconstructing the road network, our approach builds a new geometric representation that aids visualization and spatial analysis. Our representation preserves almost completely topological (e.g., connectivity, continuity, adjacency) and metric properties (e.g., geometric accuracy, distances, length), along with aggregated attributes such as road type, speed limit, number of lanes, and presence of bridges and tunnels.

We use openly accessible data from OpenStreetMap (OSM) due to its openness, accuracy, and lack of usage restrictions. Recent studies in transportation and urban walkability, such as Cohen (2024) and Meng et al. (2022), have highlighted the power of OSM data while emphasizing the importance of simplifying its street networks.

Although OSM provides high-resolution street network data globally (Boeing and Ha, 2024), its representation is often highly fragmented, as each junction, intersection, or bifurcation introduces additional nodes, breaking the streets into excessively short segments. Figure 1 displays an example of this phenomenon, showing OSM representation of street segments in central Dublin.

Cohen (2024) proposes a methodology for simplifying lanes of the same road into a unified fictitious geometry. While valuable, this does not fully address the challenge of creating a continuous representation of roads, i.e., the creation of streets defined as paths of street segments connected based on the principle of good continuity (Zhang et al., 2018).

This work reconstructs the road network into a coherent structure to support the analysis of pollutants along routes. While this paper focuses on Dublin as a case study, our methodology has been tested on different European urban networks, with source code and case studies available on GitHub (github.com/luisalopresti/OSMRoadAssembler).

2 Methodology

We retrieved OSM street network for Dublin using the *osmnx* Python library by Boeing (2017). The original Dublin street network has 26,686 edges. The high level of detail fragments routes into short street segments. Our calculations show that 50% of road segments are shorter than ~ 71 meters, with an average length of ~ 93 meters. This fragmentation occurs primarily because OSM introduces a node at every intersection, splitting roads into smaller segments. Additionally, changes in road attributes, such as speed limits or lane counts, create additional segmentation, increasing the complexity of the network representation. This creates overlapping geometries and redundancies that can be undesirable for many types of analyses. To address this problem we have developed a simplification strategy that combines road segments into unified geometries while preserving as much as possible other relevant attributes.

Original OSM Street Network of Central Dublin

Figure 1: This figure illustrates the segments of the original Dublin street network obtained using the *osmnx* library. Within this area, there are 3346 segments, with an average length below 74 meters, a median of ~ 59 meters, ranging from ~ 1.8 meters to a maximum of 465 meters.

- **Step 1: Roundabout simplification:** roundabouts are frequently represented by multiple small segments, as each incoming road fragments the overall geometry. Using OSM `junction` attribute, which may assume values `roundabout` or `circular`, we identified and reconstructed roundabouts into a unified geometry, via `shapely`'s `linemerge` and `unary union` operations (Gillies et al., 2024). This step ensures a coherent and complete representation of intersections.
- **Step 2: Road aggregation:** we aggregated road segments based on OSM `name` attribute and spatial contiguity or proximity. Specifically, we firstly standardized road names to ensure consistency, then we grouped segments sharing the same standardized name and evaluated them iteratively for spatial proximity. Contiguous segments and edges separated by less than 0.0001 meters were merged into a single geometry via `unary union`. Adding a minimal tolerance distance between geometries was essential to merge separate lanes of the same roads into a single geometry.
- **Step 3: Handling roads with alternative names:** cases where edges reported multiple `name` attributes were treated similarly, with all alternative names considered during aggregation, ensuring a complete representation.
- **Step 4: Removal of missing names:** segments lacking OSM `name` attribute were discarded. The possibility of merging unnamed segments among themselves based on proximity was evaluated, however such segments are generally shorter and located in less critical areas of the network, such as internal residential zones. The absence of the `name` attribute itself likely indicate lower relevance.

3 Results

The final aggregated network contains 3,640 unique non-overlapping geometries, against the original 26,686 segments, significantly reducing network fragmentation and enhancing road representations. Figure 2 shows examples of the obtained representation: for each row, the first plot reports the original edges, as reported in OSM and downloaded using the *osmnx* library, while the second plot shows the final representation after the processing described in section 2. Each color defines a different edge or geometry.

The first row illustrates the different representations of Dolphin Road². In the original dataset (left plot), the road is represented by 32 separate edges, while in our reconstructed version, it is captured by a single `MultiLineString`, which encompasses both the semicircular route and the small street bifurcation. The second row in figure 2 represents Charlemont³: the original representation created several small segments to capture internal streets entering the residential area, for a total of 118 edges. Our representation unifies this section of the road into a single geometry. The last two maps display the Darndale Roundabout⁴ and the roads that converge into it, Malahide Road, Blunden Drive, and Priorswood Road. The original representation is cluttered with different segments, due to fragmentation and road geometry duplication caused by the different lanes geometries. Our processing (right plot) allows a more cohesive representation of the roads, enabling the distinction of the roundabout as a single entity, and the unification of other segments into complete streets. This approach reduces the number of geometries from 147 to just 7.

Our methodology also achieves an overall network representation with (1) sensible average length, (2) low outlier presence, and (3) the absence of overlapping geometries. The mean geometry length increased to ~ 352 meters, with 50% of the geometries below 190 meters and 75% below 391 meters. This length computation involves separately counting lanes of the same road, as the geometries are merged into a single `MultiLineString` instead of altering the network by creating a fictitious `LineString`. Nevertheless, increased average length and reduced number of geometries make our results highly satisfactory. Using the inter-quantile range (IQR), we identified 318 outliers in terms of length ($\sim 8.7\%$), with only 59 roads (1.6%) over 2km. The most significant outlier is Dublin Tunnel⁵ (also known as Airport Motorway), connecting central Dublin to the airport.

Our simplification approach effectively reduced fragmentation and removed overlaps, ensuring a compact representation of the street network that will facilitate a meaningful air quality analysis, as well as be of aid for other potential road and transportation studies. Moreover, the final network attempts to preserve road attributes from OSM, such as maximum speed, highway type, and number of lanes, through thoughtful aggregation, whereby we try to preserve the richness of details from OSM while building a more compact structure. This improved representation allows for unique pollutant concentration assignments and better insights into air quality patterns at road level.

²Example of an OSM way from Dolphin Road: <https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/4934504>

³Example of an OSM way from Charlemont: <https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/25357044>

⁴Example of an OSM way from Darndale Roundabout: <https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/334819732>

⁵<https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/23007012>

Figure 2: Example of road representations before and after processing. The left column displays the edges retrieved from OpenStreetMap for Dolphin Road, Charlemont, and Darndale Roundabout along with the converging roads, with each edge represented in a different color. The right column presents the final representation, which significantly reduces the number of geometries and provides a more compact and clear visualization.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

In this paper, we outlined our current work into simplifying street network representations for specific types of analyses, such as hyperlocal air quality analysis. By applying a combination of techniques to reconstruct roundabouts and roads based on names and proximity, we were able to create a more coherent and compact representation of Dublin’s OSM street network. Our simplified network, with 3,640 non-overlapping geometries, supports the unique assignment of pollutant levels across the street network, offering a clearer air quality picture. This aggregation resolves the fragmentation and overlapping issues inherent in the original OSM data, without sacrificing realism or introducing fictitious or invalid geometries. By offering a more meaningful representation of streets, this approach lays the foundation for more accurate air quality modeling. Ultimately, this research contributes to the development of better tools for urban planning and environmental management, with broad applicability. Our methodology has been tested on different European urban networks, demonstrating its effectiveness. The source code is available on GitHub, ensuring reproducibility and reusability of our approach.

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Biography

Luisa Lo Presti is a PhD candidate in the CRT programme in Foundations of Data Science at Maynooth University. Her research focuses on geospatial analytics and spatial machine learning for climate action, with an interest in spatial fairness and mitigating performance disparities in environmental models.

Peter Mooney is an Associate Professor of Computer Science at Maynooth University. He is a long time contributor to GISRUK conferences and is currently a member of the GISRUK National Steering Committee. He is supervising Luisa for her PhD research.

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